

Reduction of Mercuric Chloride by Tartaric Acid, Induced by Potassium Permanganate

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The kinetics of reduction of mercuric chloride by tartaric acid in presence of potassium permanganate, used as an inductor, has been studied at different temperatures. The reaction has been found to be of first order with respect to both tartaric acid and mercuric chloride in its initial stages. A tentative mechanism of the reaction has been suggested.

The kinetics of the reaction between permanganate and hydroxycarboxylic acids (glycollic lactic, malic, citric, tartaric, etc.) has been studied by many workers. Levesley and Waters¹ and Kemp and Waters² studied the oxidation of α -hydroxy-acids by manganic pyrophosphate and suggested a general oxidation scheme for these acids. A kinetic study of the reaction between acid permanganate and tartaric acid was made by Sanz and co-workers³ who suggested a two-stage reaction, first being the formation of a chelated manganic tartrate complex and second, the slow decomposition of this complex. Srivastava⁴ studied the reaction between sodium tartrate and manganic alum and obtained results similar to those for the decomposition of oxalato-complex of trivalent metals by the previous workers.

Although oxidation of tartaric acid by potassium permanganate has been extensively investigated, reduction of mercuric chloride by this acid in presence of potassium permanganate as inductor has not been adequately studied. Dhar⁵ studied this reaction in presence of potassium permanganate, potassium peroxodisulphate etc. on a semiquantitative basis. Saxena⁶ studied the kinetics of reduction of mercuric chloride by tartaric acid in presence of potassium peroxodisulphate as an inductor.

In view of the above references, we have extended our previous work⁷ on the study of reduction of mercuric chloride by tartaric acid in presence of potassium permanganate, used as an inductor, and an attempt has been made to throw light on the mechanism of the reaction.

EXPERIMENTAL

The experimental procedure adopted was the same as reported⁷ previously.

1. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 217.
2. *Ibid.*, 1954, 1192.
3. *Anales real soc. espan. fis. y quim.*, 1959, 49B, 93, 187, 565, 571.
4. *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1958, 209, 22.
5. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1917, 111, 690; *this Journal*, 1928, 5, 203.
6. Saxena, Ph. D. Thesis, Agra University, 1961.
7. Bansal *et al.*, *this Journal*, 1963, 40, 1001; 1964, 41, 790; 1965, 42, 663.
8. Glasstone, "Text Book of Physical Chemistry", 1960, pp. 1106-1110.

Influence of Temperature

The kinetics of reduction of mercuric chloride was studied at various temperatures. The results obtained at 50° are recorded in Table I and the influence of temperature is represented in Fig. 1.

FIG. 1

(Scale: 1 Div. = 3 min.)

Tartaric acid = 0.1M. HgCl₂ = KMnO₄ = 0.01M.

It is observed from Table I and Fig. 1 that the reaction after a small period of induction develops up to 15 min. after which its velocity diminishes and that the velocity constant for the first- and second-order reactions gradually fall, but the zero-order velocity constant shows a constancy after 60 min. Thus the whole course of the reaction appears to consist of three zones, viz., (i) period of induction, (ii) autocatalysis, and (iii) auto-inhibition, accompanied by a normal reaction. Similar observations were made with oxalic and malonic acids⁷.

Fig. 1 also shows that the rise of temperature increases the overall velocity of the reaction and affects its various zones. The period of induction rapidly falls (Fig. 1) and the

periods of autocatalysis and auto-inhibition are shifted to early stages. The reduction of mercuric chloride was 86% in 8 hr. at 60°. The temperature coefficient of the reaction during its normal course was found to be 2 between 50° and 60° and the corresponding energy and entropy of activation were found to be 14.9 kcal. and -24.93 e.u., respectively.

TABLE I

$(\text{CHOH.COOH})_2 = 0.2M$. $\text{HgCl}_2 = \text{KMnO}_4 = 0.01M$.
Temp. = 50°. Period of induction = 1 min. 30 sec.

Time.	Hg_2Cl_2 formed (x) (mole. l $\times 10^3$)	$K_0 \times 10^6$.	$K_1 \times 10^6$.	K_2 .
0 min.	0.000	..	..	..
15	2.250	150.00	3.986	10.91
30	2.300	3.30	2.005	8.88
60	2.400	3.30	1.090	3.08
120	2.475	1.25	0.570	1.63
180	2.550	1.25	0.306	1.16
240	2.625	1.25	0.360	0.90
300	2.700	1.25	0.250	0.78
360	2.775	1.25	0.225	0.69
420	2.850	1.25	0.201	0.63
480	2.925	1.25	0.183	0.59

Influence of the Initial Concentration of the Reactants on the Reaction Rate

The kinetics of the reaction was studied at various initial concentrations of the reactants and the initial rate of reaction for 30 min. was calculated from the $x-t$ curves. The zero-order velocity constants for the later course of the reaction were also calculated. The results are recorded in Table II.

TABLE II

Tartaric acid.	$\text{HgCl}_2 = \text{KMnO}_4 = 0.01M$. Temp. = 50°.			$(\text{CHOH.COOH})_2 = 0.1M$. $\text{KMnO}_4 = 0.01M$. Temp. = 50°.			$(\text{CHOH.COOH})_2 = 0.1M$. $\text{HgCl}_2 = 0.01M$. Temp. = 50°.		
	*Initial rate.	$K_0 \times 10^6$	HgCl_2 .	*Initial rate.	$K_0 \times 10^6$.	KMnO_4 .	*Initial rate.	$K_0 \times 10^6$.	
0.05M	5.50	1.25	0.01M	6.85	1.25	0.005M	4.75	0.83	
0.10	6.55	1.25	0.02	6.05	1.25	0.010	6.55	1.25	
0.15	7.50	1.25	0.03	7.95	1.25	0.015	7.10	1.30	
0.20	8.00	1.25	0.04	7.50	1.25	..	..	..	

* Expressed in mole litre⁻¹ min⁻¹ $\times 10^6$.

From Table II it appears that an increase of the initial concentration of any of the reactants alters the initial rate in the early stages of the reaction, but the later course of the reaction remains unaffected as is evident from the K_0 values. Incidentally, the initial rate is strictly of first order with respect to both tartaric acid and mercuric chloride (Fig. 2). A definite order with respect to potassium permanganate could not be ascertained.

FIG. 2. Influence of the initial conc. of T. A. and HgCl₂ on the initial rate.

Influence of Gases

The amount of mercurous chloride formed in 60 min. was estimated in nitrogen, oxygen and CO₂ atmospheres; the gases were separately bubbled through the reaction mixture. The results are recorded in Table III.

TABLE III

(CHOH.COOH)₀ = 0.1 M. HgCl₂ = KMnO₄ = 0.01M. Temp. = 50°.

Gas.	Calomel formed (in moles /10 ⁴).	
Nil	..	2.03
Nitrogen	..	2.80
Oxygen	..	1.05
Carbon dioxide	..	2.15

The data show that nitrogen and CO₂ exert an accelerating influence on the reduction of mercuric chloride, but the effect of oxygen is the reverse.

Influence of Glass Surface

The amount of mercurous chloride formed in 60 min. was estimated in presence of different number of glass beads to ascertain the role of surface/volume ratio. The results

show that the amount of calomel formed is the same in presence of different number of glass beads, suggesting that surface/volume ratio plays no role in the reaction.

Influence of Acids

The influence of different acids on the reduction of mercuric chloride was studied to ascertain the role of H^+ ions in the kinetics.

TABLE IV

Conditions same as in Table III.

Acid conc.	Mercurous chloride formed (in moles/litre $\times 10^4$).			
	HCl.	H_2SO_4 .	HNO_3 .	CH_3COOH .
0.01N	2.05	2.05	2.050	2.05
0.02	2.10	2.15	2.175	2.05
0.04	2.20	2.30	2.325	2.05
0.10	2.25	2.35	2.425	2.05

It appears from Table IV that most of the acids used accelerate the reduction of mercuric chloride. Acetic acid exerts no effect on the reduction of mercuric chloride. These results lead to assume that H^+ ions accelerate reduction of mercuric chloride by tartaric acid in presence of potassium permanganate as an inductor.

Influence of Salts

TABLE V

Conditions same as in Table III,

Conc. of the added salts (moles/litre).	Mercurous chloride formed in moles/litre $\times 10^4$.				
	$MnSO_4$.	KCl.	K_2SO_4 .	KNO_3 .	CH_3COONa .
0.000	2.075	2.075	2.075	2.075	2.075
0.005	..	..	2.100	..	..
0.010	1.750	1.824	2.150	2.100	..
0.020	1.650	1.650	2.199	2.100	..
0.040	1.600	1.500	..	..	..
0.050	..	..	..	..	2.250
0.010	..	..	..	..	3.100
0.200	..	..	..	..	4.000
0.300	..	..	..	..	4.050
0.400	..	..	..	..	4.000

Table V shows that $MnSO_4$ and KCl retard reduction of mercuric chloride. The retarding effect of $MnSO_4$ may be due to reversible formation of an organo-manganous salt complex which reduces the amount of tartaric acid in the solution, as suggested by Levesley and Waters¹. The inhibiting influence of KCl is due to removal of Mn^{2+} ions by the chain-breaking step:

The positive catalytic influence of K_2SO_4 may be due to the specific ion effect. In KNO_3 the inhibiting influence of one ion may become equal to the catalytic influence of the other,

thereby resulting in a neutral effect. The positive catalytic influence of sodium acetate increases with its concentration to a certain limit beyond which it becomes almost constant.

Changes in Conductance during the Course of Reaction

It is observed from Fig. 3 that the conductance falls first gradually, then rapidly and finally becomes constant during the course of the reaction. It is interesting to note that the time to attain a constancy in conductance is the same as the period of induction.

FIG. 3.

[Scale: 5 div. = 1 min.]

DISCUSSION

Tartaric acid alone, like oxalic and malonic acids, does not reduce mercuric chloride even at high temperatures. The reaction suggests that the active substance responsible for reduction of mercuric chloride is produced by the interaction of tartaric acid and potassium permanganate. One of the possible active substances responsible for bringing the reduction of mercuric chloride to mercurous state may be the CO_2^- radical, as also has been suggested for oxalic and malonic acids⁷. The various characteristics of the reaction and the negative value of entropy of activation clearly indicate that the reaction is governed by a chain mechanism⁸ similar to that proposed by the authors for oxalic and malonic acids⁷.

The various steps involved in the induced reduction of mercuric chloride may be represented as follows:

(chain breaking step)

The period of induction is the time required for formation of an unstable complex and its subsequent decomposition to produce Mn^{3+} ions which react with $C_2O_4^{2-}$ ions, obtained from the oxidation of tartaric acid, to produce finally CO_2^- radicals responsible for the reduction of mercuric chloride.

An increase in temperature decreases the period of induction and increases the rate of autocatalysis due to the fact that at high temperatures the complex decomposes earlier and at a faster rate.

The catalysing influence of inorganic acids, viz., HCl, H_2SO_4 , and HNO_3 , may be attributed to the faster decomposition of the complex at high hydrogen-ion concentration.

Carbon dioxide exerts a catalysing influence which may possibly be due to formation of more CO_2^- radicals.

The inhibiting influence of oxygen is due to removal of CO_2^- radicals by the chain-breaking step:

Nitrogen catalyses the reaction which may be due to removal of dissolved oxygen from the reaction mixture.

The fall in conductance seems to be due to formation of an unstable complex. Formation of an unstable complex of the type $K[Mn(C_4H_4O_6)_2]$ in the $KMnO_4$ -tartaric acid reaction has been reported by Sanz⁶. He has further observed that the complex so formed begins to decompose after a short period. On this decomposition, there should have been a rise in conductance, but a constancy is being observed which may be due to the fact that $C_2O_4^{2-}$ ions, which are formed (vide equation 5), are consumed for the reduction of mercuric chloride, as represented by equations 6-9.

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